

Lucas variants on demand

Adolf Cusmariu
adolcus@gmail.com

In a previous article [1] the variable connector

$$x = w - 1/w$$

lead to a general expression for n^{th} increment d_n

$$d_n \equiv w^n + (-1)^n (w)^{-n}$$

as a sum of weighted powers of x :

$$d_n = \sum c_{nm} x^m, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \quad m = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

In a way, the increment function d_n can be thought as a generator of the array c_{nm} .

The resulting lower-triangular matrix $\{c_{nm}\}$ had sums across rows equal to Lucas numbers:

$$\sum_m c_{nm} = L_n$$

The identity that for any prime $p > 2$

$$L_p \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$$

discovered numerically in [1] on a small scale, is well-known [2]. However, the claim of the converse is false; for (non-primes) $n = 705, 2465,$ and 2737 [2]

$$L_n \equiv 1 \pmod{n}.$$

Now, the more general connector

$$x = w - k/w$$

explored in [1] only for $k = 1$, has led here to an expression for

$$d_n(k) \equiv w^n + (-1)^n (k/w)^{-n} = \sum c(k)_{nm} x^m, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \quad m = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

A small section of the array $c(k)_{nm}$ is shown in Table 1. below, in EXCEL shorthand; thus $c(k)_{62} = 9k^2$ means

$$c(k)_{62} = 9k^2 = k^2 c_{62}$$

m→	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
n↓	x^0	x^1	x^2	x^3	x^4	x^5	x^6	x^7	x^8	x^9	x^{10}
0	2										
1	0	1									
2	2k	0	1								
3	0	3k	0	1							
4	2k ²	0	4k	0	1						
5	0	5k ²	0	5k	0	1					
6	2k ³	0	9k ²	0	6k	0	1				
7	0	7k ³	0	14k ²	0	7k	0	1			
8	2k ⁴	0	16k ³	0	20k ²	0	8k	0	1		
9	0	9k ⁴	0	30k ³	0	27k ²	0	9k	0	1	
10	2k ⁵	0	25k ⁴	0	50k ³	0	35k ²	0	10k	0	1

Table 1.

As an example, the **actual** numerical section of the array $\mathbf{C}(3)_{nm}$ is shown below in Table 2.

m→	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
n↓	x^0	x^1	x^2	x^3	x^4	x^5	x^6	x^7	x^8	x^9	x^{10}
0	2										
1	0	1									
2	6	0	1								
3	0	9	0	1							
4	18	0	12	0	1						
5	0	45	0	15	0	1					
6	54	0	81	0	18	0	1				
7	0	189	0	126	0	21	0	1			
8	162	0	432	0	180	0	24	0	1		
9	0	729	0	810	0	243	0	27	0	1	
10	486	0	2025	0	1350	0	315	0	30	0	1

Table 2.

Numerical observations.

1. The diagonal terms $\mathbf{C}(k)_{nn} = 1, n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, \mathbf{C}(k)_{00} = 2$
2. The next diagonal $\mathbf{C}(k)_{n,n-1} = 0, n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$
3. The first column $\mathbf{C}(k)_{n,0} = k^{n/2}(1 + (-1)^n), n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$
4. A more general zigzag rule holds:

$$\mathbf{(Z}_k) \quad k\mathbf{C}(k)_{nm} + \mathbf{C}(k)_{n+1,m-1} = \mathbf{C}(k)_{n+2,m}$$

A 32 x 32 array $\{\mathbf{c}(k)_{nm}\}$ was generated in EXCEL using the above observations.

5. Some surprises; sums across rows for $k = 1$ still yielded (as expected) Lucas numbers:

$$\sum_m \mathbf{c}(1)_{nm} = L_n$$

In addition

$$\sum_m c(2)_{nm} = 2^n + (-1)^n$$

These are (mostly) Mersenne numbers, also known as **Jacobsthal-Lucas** numbers, and listed in the **OEIS** as sequence **A014551**.

Now, for $k = 3, 4, 5, \dots$, let

$$S(k)_n = \sum_m c(k)_{nm}$$

Perhaps apparent from the zigzag rule **(Z_k)**, these summing sequences should satisfy:

$$S(k)_n = S(k)_{n-1} + kS(k)_{n-2}$$

Indeed so, and the resulting sequences are variants of Lucas sequences, many listed in the **OEIS**:

S(3)_n is **OEIS** sequence **A075118**

S(4)_n is **OEIS** sequence **A072265**

S(5)_n is **OEIS** sequence **A085487**

S(6)_n is **OEIS** sequence **A087451**

S(7)_n : 2, 1, 15, 22, 127, 281, 1170, 3137, 11327, 33286, is not listed in the **OEIS**

and so on. Negative integer values for **k** also yield Lucas variants; thus

S(-1)_n is **OEIS** sequence **A057079**.

S(-2)_n is **OEIS** sequence **A002249**

S(-3)_n is **OEIS** sequence **A131040**

S(-4)_n is **OEIS** sequence **A272931**

S(-5)_n : 2, 1, -9, -14, 31, 101, -54, -559, -289, 2506, ... is not listed in the **OEIS**

S(-6)_n : 2, 1, -11, -17, 49, 151, -143, -1049, -191, 6103, ... is not listed in the **OEIS**

S(-7)_n : 2, 1, -13, -20, 71, 211, -286, -1763, 239, 12580, ... is also not listed in the **OEIS**

and many more.

References

[1] A. Cusmariu, 'More than meets the eye', <https://zenodo.org/records/14726758>, 2025

[2] T. Koshy, 'Fibonacci and Lucas Numbers with Applications', 2nd Ed., Wiley, 2018, Ch. 23, p.470.